

**SCHOOL OF PLANNING AND ARCHITECTURE NEW DELHI -110002
(DEPARTMENT OF ARCHITECTURE)**

Dated: 3rd May 2023

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NOTICE

**TO THE STUDIO COORDINATOR, STUDIO DIRECTORS AND FACULTY OF FIRST
YEAR, BACHELORS OF ARCHITECTURE.**

‘Asbestos in all forms, including chrysotile, is a carcinogenic material¹’, ‘the exposure of which occurs through ‘inhalation of fibres in air in the working environment, ambient air in the vicinity of point sources such as factories handling asbestos, or indoor air in housing and buildings containing friable (crumbly) asbestos materials.’²

In this regard, when teaching the subject of Building Construction, or any other related subject, where sloping roofs or roofing materials like roofing sheets is taught, the following suggestions are recommended:

1. Faculty is humbly urged to teach materials other than asbestos containing materials. This includes practical demonstration to students.
2. Faculty is humbly urged to tell the students the dangers of using asbestos containing materials.
3. While revising the syllabus for Bachelor of Architecture at the School of Planning and Architecture, New Delhi, the above facts will be included.

This is for your information and necessary action, wherever suitable.

Anil Dewan

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Sources:

1. <https://www.who.int/teams/environment-climate-change-and-health/chemical-safety-and-health/health-impacts/chemicals/asbestos>
2. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/asbestos-elimination-of-asbestos-related-diseases>